

LGPR: A VERSATILE GROUND PENETRATING RADAR FOR LUNAR SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION AND THE DETECTION OF BURIED WATER ICE

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Introduction: The geological history of the Moon is made of impacts, space weathering and volcanism. The lunar subsurface holds a record of these processes and of their chronology in the form of the superposition of layers of ejecta debris, regolith and solidified lava flows [see [1] for a review]. Such a record can be investigated in a non-destructive way by Ground Penetrating Radars (GPR). LGPR (Lunar GPR) is a GPR built at LATMOS (Guyancourt, France), under CNES fundings. It is designed to be accommodated on a rover to image the lunar subsurface down to several tens of meters with a centimetric resolution in the first meters below the surface and a decimetric resolution below. Its immediate science objectives are (i) characterizing the subsurface of the rover exploration zone in terms of structure and composition, (ii) searching for pockets of water ice. For this latter objective, LGPR will be combined with geophones developed at IGP (Paris, France). LGPR will be key to understand the geological history of the rover landing site and exploration zone (most likely in the lunar South pole) and provides inputs for the inventory of the lunar resources of possible interest to human exploration (water ice, regolith, lava tubes).

GPRs on the Moon: To date, only two rover-mounted GPR systems have been used for lunar subsurface investigations: the two Lunar Penetrating Radars (LPR) deployed during the Chang'e-3 and Chang'e-4 missions (CNSA) [2,3]. Both LPR instruments included a high-frequency channel operating at a central frequency of 500 MHz, designed to probe the upper tens of meters of the subsurface with decimetric resolution (typically ~30 cm). In the Mare Imbrium region, near Laplace crater, the Chang'e-3 LPR achieved a penetration depth of approximately 10 m [2,4]. In contrast, the Chang'e-4 LPR, operating near Von Kármán crater on the lunar farside and closer to the south pole, imaged subsurface structures down to depths of about 40 m [2,5]. More specifically, LPR data collected along the 320 m traverse of the Yutu-2 rover at the Chang'e-4 landing site indicate that a ~12 m thick fine-grained regolith layer overlies a sequence of multiple ejecta deposits. The greater penetration depth observed in the Chang'e-4 exploration area suggests the presence of low-attenuation materials, which are particularly favorable for radio sounding.

Most upcoming lunar rover missions are expected to carry GPR instruments. Examples include the LPR

onboard Chang'e-7 and the L-MAPS instrument—a combined GPR and microwave radiometer—planned for NASA's Lunar Terrain Vehicle (LTV). Importantly, unlike their predecessors, these new GPR systems are designed with polarimetric capabilities. Polarimetric measurements can be used to construct the Circular Polarization Ratio (CPR) defined as the ratio of the power returned in the same sense of circular polarization as transmitted (SC) to that returned in the opposite sense (OC). The CPR is a parameter widely used in planetary radar data analysis as it serves as an indicator of surface and subsurface roughness and can even provide a powerful diagnostic for distinguishing between ice and rock (see Harrar et al., this conference). Anomalously high values of the CPR has been recorded by the orbital radar Mini-RF in the Permanently Shadowed Regions (PSR) of the Moon, which are suspected to host large quantities of water ice in their subsurface [5].

LGPR: a GPR with full-polarimetry capabilities and combinable with geophones: LGPR is an ultra wideband step-frequency polarimetric GPR operating in the 200 MHz-2 GHz frequency range. Although operating at lower frequencies to probe greater depths, LGPR builds upon the heritage of WISDOM (Water, Ice and Subsurface Deposit Observation on Mars), the GPR developed for the ExoMars Rosalind Franklin rover [6] (ESA mission scheduled for launch to Mars in 2028). Like WISDOM, LGPR will be capable of acquiring data in four linear polarization configurations, provided it is mounted on a rover large enough to accommodate a pair of antennas. Several LGPR versions are currently under development, with the aim of proposing the most versatile concept (with polarimetric but also bi-static and multi-channel capabilities) while remaining within strict volume and mass constraints (1U for the electronic box, <1.5 kg total). In all versions, unlike WISDOM, LGPR will record both in-phase (I) and quadrature (Q) components and will implement a gating technique to increase its dynamic range, thereby enhancing its ability to image deeper subsurface features.

Figure 1 presents the expected performance of LGPR in terms of sounding depth and vertical resolution for two types of terrain: one characterized by relatively high attenuation, such as the Chang'e-3 landing site, and one with lower attenuation, similar to the Chang'e-4 landing site. The results indicate that, at a

Chang'e-4-like site, LGPR will be capable of imaging the subsurface down to depths of approximately 50 m, with centimetric resolution within the upper 5 m and decametric resolution at greater depths.

The electronic architecture of LGPR also enables coupling the GPR with a system of up to six geophones, which will be mounted on the rover and operated as a rotaphone [7]. This feature is particularly relevant for the detection of shallow water-ice reservoirs, as geophones are sensitive to mechanical properties, whereas electromagnetic waves primarily respond to electrical and structural properties. Large variations are observed for as low as 1% of ice content, and for larger one, seismic velocities can more than double [8]. For example, if water ice is intimately mixed with the lunar regolith, it may be difficult to detect using GPR measurements alone; however, geophones would be more likely to identify it.

Conclusion: In this presentation, we will describe LGPR science objectives, design, and expected performance, as well as its development plan and flight opportunities.

References: [1] Crawford et al., 2020, *Int. J. Imp. Eng.*, 137 [2] Fang et al., *Res. Astron. Astrophys.* 2014, 14, 1607–1622. [3] Li C. et al. *Sci. Adv.* 2020, 6, eaay6898 [4] Lai et al. *Planet. Space Sci.* 2016, 120, 96–102. [4] Lai et al. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 2019, 46, 12783–12793 [5] Li S. et al. (2018), *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, 115, 8907-8912. [6] Ciarletti et al., 2017, *Astrobiology* 17 (6-7), 565 - 584. [7] Brokešová et al., *Rev. Sci. Instrum.*, 83, 086108. (2012) [8] Tsuji et al. *Icarus*, 404:115666 (2023).

Fig. 1: Estimated performances of LGPR for two types of terrain (Chang'e3-like and Chang'e4-like) and a smooth or rough buried interface overlaid by a basaltic regolith layer: detection depth as a function of LGPR operating frequencies and vertical resolution as a function of depth.